

ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC GRANT AGREEMENT NO 676550

DELIVERABLE REPORT

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GOVERNANCE BODIES OF ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC

The organizational structure of ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC (Fig 1) will follow the governance structure of BBMRI-ERIC with few adjustments. This document describes the composition and roles of the different governance bodies of ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC: General Assembly, Steering Committee and the International Advisory Committee.

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Document log

Issue	Date	Comment	Author/partner
D1.1-Rev1	2017-08-16	Inclusion of EU funding recognition to comply with Grant Agreement art. 29.4. Updates on Deliverable Template.	Outi Törnwall

This project has received funding from the *European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 676550.

Coordination

The Director General of BBMRI-ERIC will act as the Coordinator of ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC, supported by the Central Executive and Management Office (CEMO) of BBMRI-ERIC. The Director General is Prof. Jan-Eric Litton and the Project Manager of the ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC is Dr. Outi Törnwall.

General Assembly of ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC

The General Assembly (GA) of ADOPT project is represented by the Assembly of Members of BBMRI-ERIC. It consists of representatives (Table 1) of all legal entities of BBMRI-ERIC and will meet once a year in person. GA decides on the overall policy, budget issues and approves the annual reports.

The Steering Committee of ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC

The Steering Committee (SC) of ADOPT project is represented by the Management Committee of BBMRI-ERIC. It consists of all ADOPT Work Package (WP) leaders (Table 2), who as well are the National Node Directors of BBMRI-ERIC. The CEMO organizes monthly meetings for the SC (teleconferences / meetings in person). The SC is responsible for preparing the decisions for the General Assembly and the day-to-day management of their WPs as well as the development of the performance indicators.

The International Advisory Committee

WP1 is responsible for setting up an International Advisory Committee (IAC), which is the one body that will be specifically set up for this project. The IAC consists of international leaders of the scientific community and will schedule a meeting yearly.

The IAC will ensure scientific excellence as well as the compliance with the needs of industry and society. It will promote dissemination and provide visions for the structuring and operation of activities of ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC. Ultimately, it will enlarge the connections towards stakeholders and users of the implemented infrastructure. The five leading experts (coming from the fields of clinical and population based biobanking, ELSI and IT) of IAC (Table 3) will advise ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC in all relevant matters. The IAC is chaired by Prof Eero Vuorio (former Director of Biocenter Finland).

One member, due to a conflict of interest, has changed in the original set up of the IAC in Oct 2015. Prof Jane Kaye (Oxford University, UK) has been replaced by Dr. Deborah Mascalzoni from Uppsala University, Sweden.

Fig. 1 The governance structure of ADOPT BBMRI-ERI

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Table 1. The General Assembly of ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC

General Assembly (=Assembly of members of BBMRI-ERIC)		
Name	Organisation	
Dr. Hemma Bauer	BMWWF	Austria
Mr. Oliver Mayer	BMWWF	Austria
Prof. Kurt Zatloukal	Medizinische Universität Graz	Austria
Cornelia Stumptner	Medizinische Universität Graz	Austria
Mr Didier Flagothier	Federal Public Planning Service Science Policy BELSPO	Belgium
Mrs. Michele Oleo	EWI	Belgium
Mr Philippe Desmeth	BELSPO	Belgium
Dr. Dalibor Valík	Masaryk Memorial Cancer Institute	Czech
Kristina Greplova		Czech
Petr Ventluka	Ministry of education, Youth and sports	Czech
Dr. Toivo Rääim	Ministry of Education and Research	Estonia
Priit Tamm	Estonian Research Council	Estonia
Riina Vuorento	Ministry of Education and Culture	Finland
Anneli Törrönen	Ministry of Social Affairs and Health	Finland
Heli Salminen-Mankonen	Docent, Auria Biobank	Finland
Eero Vuorio	University of Helsinki	Finland
Veli-Matti Kosma		Finland
Claire Levy-Marchal	INSERM	France
Dr. Georges Dagher	INSERM	France
Leopold Fezeu	Université Paris 13	France

Dr. Hemma Bauer	BMWFV	Austria
Mr. Oliver Mayer	BMWFV	Austria
Prof. Kurt Zatloukal	Medizinische Universität Graz	Austria
Cornelia Stumptner	Medizinische Universität Graz	Austria
Mr Didier Flagothier	Federal Public Planning Service Science Policy BELSPO	Belgium
Mrs. Michele Oleo	EWI	Belgium
Mr Philippe Desmeth	BELSPO	Belgium
Dr. Dalibor Valík	Masaryk Memorial Cancer Institute	Czech
Kristina Greplova		Czech
Petr Ventluka	Ministry of education, Youth and sports	Czech
Dr. Toivo Rääm	Ministry of Education and Research	Estonia
Priit Tamm	Estonian Research Council	Estonia
Riina Vuorento	Ministry of Education and Culture	Finland
Anneli Törrönen	Ministry of Social Affairs and Health	Finland
Heli Salminen-Mankonen	Docent, Auria Biobank	Finland
Eero Vuorio	University of Helsinki	Finland
Veli-Matti Kosma		Finland
Claire Levy-Marchal	INSERM	France
Dr. Georges Dagher	INSERM	France
Leopold Fezeu	Université Paris 13	France
Paul Hofman	Hôpital Pasteur	France
Bruno Clément	INSERM	France
Dr. Joachim Klein	Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung	Germany

Dr. Isabell Hahn	DLR	Germany
Prof. Dr. Michael Hummel	Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin	Germany
Cornelia Rufenach	Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin	Germany
Dr. Sossana Kolyva	Institute Pasteur	Greece
Dr. Dimitris Thanos	Academy of Athens	Greece
Dr. Luca Sangiorgi	Istituto Ortopedico Rizzoli di Bologna	Italy
Paola Giovannini		Italy
Dr. Elena Bravo	ISS	Italy
Dr. Gaetano Guglielmi	Direttore Ufficio III - Ministero della Salute	Italy
Dr. Rosa Maria Martoccia	Direzione Centrale delle Risorse Economiche Istituto Superiore di Sanità Ph.	Italy
Prof. Richard Muscat	University of Malta	Malta
Prof. Dr. Alex Felice	University of Malta	Malta
Joanna Vella	University of Malta	Malta
Dr. Edvard Beem	The Netherlands Organisation for Health Research and Development ZonMW	The Netherlands
Helen Vrolijk	The Netherlands Organisation for Health Research and Development ZonMW	The Netherlands
Prof. Dr. Gert-Jan van Ommen	Leiden University Medical Center - LUMC	The Netherlands
Els Natziyl-Visser	Secretary of Gert-Jan van Ommen	The Netherlands

Dr. Jeannette Ridder-Numan	Ministry of Education, Culture and Science	The Netherlands
Karianne Solaas	The Research Council of Norway	Norway
Bjørn Jacobsen	The Research Council of Norway	Norway
Anna Chróścicka	Medical University of Warsaw	Poland
Dominik STRAPAGIEL	Dept. of Molecular Biophysics University of Lodz	Poland
Dr. Lukasz Kozera	Wrocław Research Centre EIT +	Poland
Dr. Katrin Brandt	Swedish Research Council (Vetenskapsrådet)	Sweden
Prof. Maria Anvret	Göteborgs universitet	Sweden
Dr. Ayşim Yılmaz	SNSF	Switzerland
Dr. Stéphanie Wyss	SNSF	Switzerland
Prof. Nese Atabey	University of Dokuz Eylul	Turkey
Dr Jon Fistein	Medical Research Council	UK
Dr. Louisa Rahemtulla	Medical Research Council	UK
Dr. Maimuna Mendy	IARC	France
Sally Moldan	LSB Assistant of Dr. Maimuna Mendy	France

Table 2. Steering Committee of ADOPT

Steering Committee/Work Package leaders (=Management committee of BBMRI-ERIC)			
WP	WP name	WP leader	Institute/ Organization
WP1	Coordination	Prof Jan-Eric Litton Dr Outi Törnwall (Project Manager)	BBMRI-ERIC, Austria
WP2	Datasets	Prof Marialuisa Lavitrano Dr Georges Dagher (co-lead)	University of Milano - Bicocca, Italy
WP3	Gateway	Prof Michael Hummel Prof Andres Metspalu (co-lead)	Charité, Germany Estonian Genome Center, Estonia
WP4	Access	Dr Georges Dagher Prof Marialuisa Lavitrano (co-lead)	INSERM, France
WP5	ELSI & Stakeholder Forum	Prof Anne Cambon Thomsen	University of Toulouse, France
WP6	Biomarker development	Prof Kurt Zatloukal Dr Anu Jalanko (co-lead)	Medical University of Graz, Austria Institute for Health and Welfare, Finland
WP7	Rare Diseases	Dr Luca Sangiorgi Prof Gert-Jan van Ommen (co-lead)	Rizzoli Orthopedic Institute, Italy Leiden University Medical Center, Netherlands
WP8	Internationalization	Mr Markus Pasterk	BBMRI-ERIC, Austria

Table 3. The International Advisory Committee of BBMRI-ERIC

International Advisory Committee		
Name		Institute/ Organization
Dr	Isabelle Fortier	McGill University Health Center, Canada
Prof	Rongxing Gan	Shanghai Clinical Research Center, China
Dr	Deborah Mascalzoni	Center for Research Ethics and Bioethics, Sweden
Dr	Jim Vaught	ISBER president, USA
Prof	Eero Vuorio	Former Director Biocenter Finland, Finland

References

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